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A Survey on Posture Recognition in Bharathanatyam images

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Abstract: Posture recognition is a critical element of Bharathanatyam, a classical Indian dance form, characterized by intricate footwork, graceful movements, and expressive gestures. Automating posture recognition in Bharathanatyam images is essential for preserving this cultural art form while leveraging modern technological advancements. This survey examines existing methods and technologies for posture recognition, with a specific focus on Bharathanatyam poses. It provides an extensive review of datasets, techniques, and models, including traditional machine learning approaches like SVM and HOG features, as well as advanced deep learning models such as CNNs and LSTMs. The paper highlights the challenges in dataset preparation, feature extraction, and model accuracy due to variations in dancer attributes, lighting, and pose complexity. By systematically analyzing state-of-the-art techniques and their applications in related domains, this survey aims to bridge gaps and propose future directions for improving the precision and robustness of Bharathanatyam posture recognition systems.

Keywords: Bharathanatyam, posture recognition, deep learning, machine learning, feature extraction.

1. Introduction

Bharathanatyam is a traditional Indian dance form that has a rich history and is deeply rooted in Indian culture and tradition. It is characterized by its intricate footwork, graceful movements of the body, expressive hand gestures, and elaborate facial expressions. According to Hindu tradition, the name of this dance style is a combination of the words 'Bharatha' and 'Natyam', where 'Natyam' means 'dance' in Sanskrit and 'Bharatha' is a combination of the words "bha", "ra", and "tha" stands for 'bhava', 'raga' and 'tala' that represent emotion, melody and rhythm respectively. Therefore, the term Bharathanatyam usually refers to a dance style that expresses bhavam, ragam, and thalam (Padma Subramaniam 2015).

Bharathanatyam dance is not only a beautiful and mesmerizing art form, but also carries cultural and spiritual significance. It is deeply rooted in India's rich heritage and represents the essence of Hindu mythology and scriptures. Bharathanatyam serves as a medium for storytelling, with intricate hand gestures and expressive facial expressions conveying deep emotions and narratives. This dance form is also a powerful and highly disciplined way of maintaining physical and mental well-being. It demands rigorous training, which not only helps in improving flexibility, strength, and stamina, but also fosters discipline and dedication. Bharathanatyam is a profound way of connecting with one's inner self and is a means of self-expression, introspection, and self-discovery. It plays a crucial role in preserving and promoting India's cultural traditions and serves as a source of inspiration and pride for dancers and audiences alike. Posture refers to the position and orientation of different parts of the body, such as the spine, limbs, and head, relative to each other and the environment. Correct posture involves maintaining a balanced, neutral alignment of the body that allows for optimal support, stability, and function. Posture in dance refers to the specific position and orientation of the body that a dancer takes when performing various movements and routines. These postures play an important role in conveying emotion, expressing artistic intent, and maintaining proper technique.

One of the fundamental aspects of Bharathanatyam is the emphasis on various poses called 'mandi' which form the building blocks of the dance vocabulary. A very important step in learning the Bharathanatyam dance form involves learning the different Bharathanatyam postures. Without posture, dance form has no meaning. Developing and mastering the correct Bharathanatyam posture requires patience, diligence, and practice (<https://learn.podium.school/bharatanatyam/bharatanatyam-postures-for-beginners/>) and Table 1.1 shows the basic postures of the Bharathanatyam dance form.

Table 1.1 Basic Postures of Bharathanatyam Dance Form

S.No.	Posture Name	Posture	Description
1.	Samapadam		Samapadam is the first and basic posture in Bharathanatyam. It is also called Sthanakam (https://learn.podium.school/bharathanatyam/bharathanatyam-postures-for-beginners/). In this basic position, the body is held upright with the knees slightly bent to achieve a balanced position. The legs are lined up without space.
2.	Aramandi		This posture is most commonly used in Bharathanatyam. When this pose is done, it can completely change the look of the dance. Aramandi (Ardhamandalam) or Ayatham can be performed by making the third quarter of the body and turning the legs sideways to stabilize the body.
3.	Muzhumandi		The Muzhumandi pose is the most perfect seated pose in Bharathanatyam, where the feet remain in the same position as the Aramandi pose. In this position, the thighs are stretched in the opposite direction, the heels are held together and the feet apart to balance the body.

Posture recognition involves the capacity to identify and scrutinize the positioning and movements of the human body, often employing technologies like cameras, sensors, or machine learning algorithms. Its utility spans various fields such as healthcare, sports, ergonomics, and human-computer interaction. Within the realm of dance, it harmoniously blends technology and artistic expression to elevate the dance experience. Thus, research endeavors are necessary to advance methods for the automatic recognition of a dancers postures in a given image.

The development of an approach to automatically recognize the Bharathanatyam postures can be attributed to several factors. Posture recognition refers to the ability to detect and analyze the position and movements of the human body, typically using technologies such as cameras, sensors or machine learning algorithms. It has many applications in, for example, healthcare, sports, ergonomics, and human-computer interaction. It combines technology and art to create a complete and enriching dance experience. Reasons for identifying postures in dance include technique improvement, injury prevention, aesthetic quality, expressive communication, feedback and guidance, monitoring consistency and progress, skill development, and promoting the overall quality of dance performances.

2. Related work

Xiaodan Hu *et al.*, (2021) developed a Hierarchical Dance video recognition model framework for extracting body motion and dance genres. The framework was used to create a new UIL Dataset (University of Illinois Dance) containing 1143 video clips from 9 dance genres spanning 30 hours, annotated with dance movement and dance genre descriptors, 154 movement types, and 16 body parts. The LSTM network was used for 3D movement subsequence extraction for dance genre recognition, receiving an F- score of 86%. Using a Kinect sensor to capture depth images, Wen June Wang *et al.*, (2015) were able to identify the five different human postures (Sitting, Standing, Stooping, Kneeling, and Lying) using a LVQ neural network. They classified postures using LVQ and identified Horizontal projection, Vertical projection, and Star Skeleton for body position information and achieved an accuracy of 99%.

Matthias Dantone *et al.*, (2013) relied on still images to predict 2D human poses. Specifically, they used 2-layer random forests as common denominators. The first layer acts as a discriminant independent classifier for body parts. The second layer takes the first layer's estimated class distributions and predicts joint locations by modeling how it interacts with each other and how they co-occur. They used 2 datasets: the famous 'Leeds Sports Pose' dataset and the newly collected 'FashionPose' dataset. The LSP dataset contains a large number of poses, but the variation of look and dress style across each of the 8 sport classes is relatively small. They collected a new dataset 'Fashion pose' with a high degree of fabric and appearance variation and achieved 55.5% accuracy.

In this study, Rinki Gupta *et al.*, (2020) used a wearable sensor to detect normal or abnormal human body posture using three tri-axis accelerometers placed at the backs of seven volunteers. This study used nine different sitting or standing postures to classify the human body. For posture classification, a novel hybrid deep learning model comprising of a Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) and a Long Short-Term Model (LSTM) was developed. The combined FCN-LSTM network produces the highest average classification accuracy of 99.91%, whereas the individual FCN and LSTM networks produce classification accuracies of 97.88% and 88.47%, respectively. The models' complexity and execution time were also compared.

A study conducted by Xue Yang (2021) compared two approaches to motion state detection: vision-based and sensor-based. The vision-based approach relied on the use of hardware, the cost of the device, the ability to tolerate errors, and the accuracy of the measurements. The sensor-based approach, however, was heavily reliant on an inertial sensor, and was based on the detection of motion information from camera acquired images.

Furthermore, node sampling and fusion data measurement of the primary joints in the human body were conducted, using band binding as well as other methods. The results of this study provided insight into human behavior.

Lei Zhao (2019) used inertial sensor technology to distinguish four basketball postures: dribbling, passing, catching, and shooting. Four nine-axis inertial sensors worn on the arm captured the data. After smoothing and normalizing, the time domain and frequency domain characteristics were recovered. Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used to recognize posture using the 30 eigenvectors produced by dimensionality reduction achieved through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) resulting in a recognition accuracy of 96% against the Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) whose recognition accuracy was 85.4%.

Weili Ding (2020) described a method for recognizing human posture based on skeleton information derived from a Kinect sensor. Multiple features, including angle and distance features between joints, were defined. Then, using bagging and random subspace approaches, rule ensembles based on the RIPPER rule learning algorithm were created, allowing training 100 rule sets that comprise a rule ensemble for final classification by majority voting. Three datasets were retrieved from public action databases MSR-Action3D, Microsoft MSRC-12, and UTKinect-Action, and a fourth dataset "Baduanjin posture" was created using the Kinect sensor. They ran thorough tests on these four datasets and attained accuracy rates of 94.5%, 97.6%, 98.1%, and 99.6%, respectively.

Qian Zhou *et al.*, (2020) developed a machine learning framework to identify and assess the basic movements of Chinese traditional dance practiced by a coach and participants. The five joint point coordinates of three sets of images were generated using TensorFlow and OpenPose. The coordinates of the joint positions between the pictures were translated and scaled, with the neck as the focal point. The similarity of the coordinate matrix was then evaluated to determine if the participants' actions met the criteria for qualification. To identify the similarity of the joint coordinates, the authors employed the Cosine similarity method in Sklearn.metrics, as well as the pairwise module.

Aayush Gupta *et al.*, (2018) designed a learning game for toddlers to learn simple dance steps that motivate them to execute a position that matches the dance moves presented. Their goal was to replace the traditional skeletal tracking provided by devices like Microsoft Kinect with a single camera. They derived the positions of the major human body joints from an individual 2D image. The OpenPose Deep Learning package was used to detect key points in the human body and hand, as well as in the face, on single photographs. This data was then used to calculate eighteen body key points associated with major human body joints. A neural network was then used in the processing pipeline to accept the input image, resulting in the generation of body part confidence heatmaps and Part Affinity Fields (PAFs). This data was then compared to determine the location of body part joints in the image. The authors also compared training times for different strategies to aid model improvement.

Jin Mu (2022) focused on the synthesis of images and videos based on the key points of a human pose, and divided the pose transformation of a person into two sub-tasks. These sub-tasks involved the extraction of features from the joint points of the human pose by the estimation method and the image synthesis by the use of

the Generative Adversarial Network. Subsequently, the proposed technique was evaluated on the YouTube Data-18 dataset and the DeepFashion dataset.

Sriparna Saha (2015) developed an automated method for identifying 20 early ballet dance positions. The skin color segmentation was used to classify dance postures. The output of the segmentation was then diluted and processed to produce skeletons of the initial postures. Staggered stick figure diagrams were transubstantiated in order to confirm the affirming reduced skeletons. The skeletons are full of small abnormalities. The 20 postures were divided into five categories according to their Euler number, and the initial database group was populated with line integral plots for the fundamental postures with their Euler numbers, and an empirically determined threshold was used to determine the accuracy of the accomplished posture. Overall, the proposed approach achieved a precision of 91.35%, including the recognition of unknown postures.

The objective of Sriparna Saha's (2017) work was to develop a fuzzy matching algorithm capable of recognizing seventeen ballet dance primitives automatically. Skin color segmentation was applied to the dance postures and the minimized skeletons of the postures were generated. Straight line approximation of the minimized skeletons using chain code and sampling generated their corresponding stick figure diagrams. The fuzzy membership of the postures with respect to the four quadrants was assessed. Utilizing the evaluated data, T-norm operator was able to determine the proximity of the generated dance posture with a precision of 84.6%.

Gautam (2017) proposed a system for the recognition of 50 postures taken from 9 distinct Bharathanatyam videos with various background. The histogram of oriented gradient (HOG) features were extracted and Support Vector Machine (SVM) was implemented to identify the pose. After experimenting with different cell sizes, it was concluded that a cell size of [8,8] resulted in an accuracy of 99.39%.

The objective of Shubhangi (2017) work was to identify poses in three dance forms, Bharathanatyam, Kathak and Odissi. Fifteen poses from the three dance forms were taken into account for the pose classification problem, with a total of 100 images selected. Hu moments were selected for describing the shape of an image, as they are scalar, translatable and rotation-independent. The resulting images were converted to binary form and using both the one vs one and one vs all approaches of SVM classifiers, the accuracy of the results was reported as 90% and 83.33% respectively.

Tanwi Mallick (2022) conducted a study utilizing nuiCapture software to create a Dataset of 10 sets of 58 adavus with the use of a Kinect XBox 360. The dataset was then performed by nine qualified dancers for one cycle and multiple times. The key postures were extracted from the video using audio beats as well as no-motion information. Features were extracted from both the skeleton and RGB images of the Kinect, which were then used to create GMM classifiers, SVM classifiers, and CNN classifiers. The accuracy of the posture recognition was reported to be 83.04%; 97.97%; and 61.30%.

K.V.V. Kumar (2017) has developed a novel recognition model that utilizes discrete wavelet transforms and local binary patterns (LBP) for segmentation. This model was used to create four dance videos from five dancers for two songs in two distinct dance styles, as well as to collect similar online YouTube downloads of

dance performances. The classifier was fed with five types of features, which were calculated from the Zernike moment, the Hu moment, the shape signature, the LBP feature, and the Haar feature. These extracted features were then fed into the Adaboost multiclass classifier, with labels from the relevant song (tala), and the accuracy of the respective features was recorded at 96, 91, 81, 83, and 93%.

A summary of the performance measures reported in literature using various techniques for posture recognition is presented in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Summary of Performance Measures reported using Various Techniques for Posture Recognition

Author(s)	Dataset used	Classification task	Classifier used	Performance reported
Xiaodan Hu <i>et al.</i> , (2021)	University of Illinois Dance (UID) Dataset	To recognize dance genre	LSTM	86% F- score
Wen-June Wang <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Kinetic sensor	To recognize 5 postures	LVQ Neural network	99% accuracy
Matthias Dantone <i>et al.</i> , (2013)	Leeds Sports Pose and Fashion Pose	Human pose estimation	SVM	55.5% accuracy
Rinki Gupta <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	3 tri- axial accelerometers	Classify 9 sitting and standing pose	FCN	99.91% accuracy
			LSTM	97.88% accuracy
			FCN+ LSTM	88.47% accuracy
Lei Zhaoa <i>et al.</i> , (2019)	4 nine-axis inertial sensors worn on arm	Recognize 4 postures of basket ball player	BPNN	85.4% accuracy
			SVM	96% accuracy
Weili Ding <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	MSR-Action3D	Human posture recognition	RIPPER rule learning	94.5% accuracy
	Microsoft MSRC-12			97.6% accuracy
	UTKinect-Action			98.1% accuracy
	Baduanjin posture			99.6% accuracy
Jin Mu	YouTube Dancer-18 and Deep	Dance tracking	LSTM-PCA	3.61 Consistency score

(2022)	Fashion		LSTM-PCA + Discriminator	5.43 Consistency score
			LSTM-PCA + Discriminator + Generator	6.90 Consistency score
			Generator + Discriminator	7.85 Consistency score
			Generator + Discriminator + Auto encoder	8.52 Consistency score
Sriparna Saha <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	YouTube videos	Identifying 20 primitive Ballet postures	Skeleton with Euler number	91.35% accuracy
Sriparna Saha <i>et al.</i> , (2017)	YouTube videos	Identifying 17 primitive Ballet postures	Fuzzy matching	84.6% accuracy
Surbhi Gautam <i>et al.</i> , (2017)	Dance videos	Identifying 50 Bharathanatyam poses	HOG+SVM	99.39% accuracy
Shubhangi <i>et al.</i> , (2017)	Database of 100 images	15 pose of Bharathanatyam, kathak and odissi	Hu-Moments + SVM (1-1)	90% accuracy
			Hu-Moments + SVM (1-N)	83.33% accuracy
Tanwi Mallick <i>et al.</i> , (2022)	Bharathanatyam Dataset	Adavus pose recognition	Skeleton + GMM	83.04% accuracy
			Skeleton + SVM	97.97% accuracy
			Skeleton + CNN	61.30% accuracy
K. V. V. Kumar <i>et al.</i> , (2017)	Bharathanatyam dance videos + YouTube videos	Pose recognition	Zernike moments + AdaBoost	96% accuracy
			Hu moments + AdaBoost	91% accuracy
			Shape signature + AdaBoost	81% accuracy
			LBP features+ AdaBoost	83% accuracy
			Haar features+ AdaBoost	93% accuracy

Developing a posture recognition system can be a difficult task since it entails a number of technical, data related, and practical issues. The model requires a large amount of labeled data, and it is difficult to collect a broad and complete dataset of postures. Posture recognition systems may be required to operate in a variety of contexts with changing illumination, background, and noise. It can be difficult to ensure the model's robustness to these conditions. This needs research that aims to address the difficulties in automatic posture detection by collecting a wide variety of images and developing a model that accurately recognizes the postures.

3. Conclusion and Future work

Automating posture recognition in Bharathanatyam images presents unique challenges due to the intricate and dynamic nature of this classical dance form. This survey has highlighted the breadth of research in the domain, showcasing various methodologies ranging from traditional feature-based approaches to advanced deep learning techniques. While substantial progress has been made, significant gaps remain, particularly in the development of comprehensive datasets, robust models capable of generalizing across diverse conditions, and frameworks addressing the cultural and artistic nuances of Bharathanatyam. Future research must prioritize the integration of multimodal data, advanced neural architectures, and domain-specific customizations to achieve more accurate and reliable recognition systems. By addressing these challenges, the field can contribute significantly to preserving and promoting Bharathanatyam through technology, ensuring its cultural relevance for future generations.

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